

Application of Geostatistics to Mineral Resource Modelling and Estimation: Case Study of Gofolo Hill Iron Ore Deposit, Western Liberia

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ABSTRACT

The viability of new mining operations depends on accurately evaluating mineral resources. Geostatistical methods are essential in providing accurate mineral resource estimation due to their ability to quantify estimation uncertainties and their ability to take spatial correlation into account. The study aims to model the orebody of the Gofolo Hill Iron Ore deposit in Western Liberia, evaluate the mineral resources using the geostatistical ordinary kriging method, and compare the results with estimates made using the inverse distance weighting method and the nearest neighbour polygon method. The study uses 39 RC drill holes with 200m x 60m grid spacing for resource modelling and estimation. The geostatistical ordinary kriging estimate of the project reported 17.169 Mt at a mean grade of 35.90%. Estimation methods are compared and correlated by descriptive statistics, grade-volume-tonnage results, and correlation coefficient. These results show that ordinary kriging, inverse distance weighting and nearest neighbour polygon have the highest accuracy in decreasing order of precision. The low standard error, low percent of global mean grade difference, and low coefficient of variation figures proved the validity of all estimating techniques.

INTRODUCTION

Mineral resource and reserve estimation is critical in progressing from mineral exploration to commodity production (Jowitt & McNulty, 2021). Mineral estimation, made possible through the interpretation of quality geological data and economic considerations, determines the viability of a mineral deposit. The estimation must be done accurately and precisely to avoid false financial expectations since mineral resource estimations are the basis for starting a mining operation (Abuntori et al., 2021). Mineral resource estimation has been an old practice that began in the 1900s and developed and progressed over a hundred years. The development has been from the classic polygonal method to the nearest neighbour method, inverse distance weighting method, and more robust geostatistical kriging methods. The traditional methods (classic polygonal, nearest neighbour, and inverse distance weighting) are often applied at the early stage of mineral resource estimation. However, these methods do not consider spatial relationships among sampled values and cannot specify the accuracy of the estimations, thus leading to subjective mineral assessment (Pandey, 2014). The two significant issues with the traditional methods, error estimation (accuracy) and spatial relationship, solved by geostatistics, have given the geostatistical method a unique role in the mineral industry and other industries. Geostatistical ordinary kriging method, inverse distance weighting method and nearest neighbour polygon method are three methods of grade interpolation regularly used for mineral estimation, comparative analysis and validation studies (Bargawa & Tobing, 2020; De-Vitry, 2003; Gong et al., 2014; Mallick et al., 2019; Shahbeik et al., 2014). The geostatistical method of estimation foundation is based on the theory of Regionalised Variables (variables with geographical location, spatial position and correlation), which Prof. Georges Matheron developed based on the practical work carried out by Daniel G. Krige in 1951 for determining the ore grades from drill cores in a South African gold mine.

The ordinary Kriging method uses a semi-variogram to quantify spatial relationships and make better estimates. It also accounts for the estimation uncertainty by minimising the error variance or prediction error. The inverse distance weighting method uses the distance between estimating points to interpolate unknown points. The assumption is that sample points closer to the unknown point are more related to the unknown point than those farther away. The nearest neighbour polygon method simply assigns the value of the closest known point to the unknown point being interpolated. The study aims to evaluate the Gofolo Hill Iron Ore deposit in Western Liberia using the geostatistical ordinary kriging method and compare the results with estimates made using the inverse distance weighting method and the nearest neighbour polygon method. To estimate the grade of iron of the Gofolo Hill deposit, blocks of dimension 50 m x 20 m x 5 m were used. All methods of estimation were completed using the Datamine Studio RM 1.13 software.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Case Study

The study area, Gofolo Hill, is located in Western Liberia, Grand Cape Mount County, approximately 80km northwest of Liberia's capital, Monrovia and 20km to the closest coastal location (Figure 1). The Gofolo Hill and two other deposits (Zaway and Koehnko) are along a strike length of the historic Bomi Hills and Bong Range projects (two operational mines in the 1960s when Liberia was Africa's top iron ore producer). The Gofolo Hill is situated over the regional northwest trending Todi Shear zone on the edge of the West African craton. The craton comprises Precambrian aged rocks – the primary geological setting of iron ore deposits worldwide. The Todi shear zone denotes the boundary between the Liberian age province (2.8 – 3.3 Ga) of Archean rocks in the north and the Pan African age province (500 Ma) of younger rocks along the Liberian coast (Gunn et al., 2018). Iron mineralisation in the area is attributed to itabirite, an indication of

banded iron formation (BIF) that has undergone regional metamorphism (folding and faulting) and recrystallisation due to the three major tectonothermal deformation events – Liberian orogeny, Eburnean orogeny and Pan African orogeny – likely to impact the study area. (Hadden, 2006; Kromah, 1974).

Figure 1: Location of the Study area

Materials

Thirty-nine reverse circulation drill holes were used for resource modelling and estimation. Information on each drill hole was distributed in four Excel tables. The Excel tables are collar, survey, assay and geology tables. The collar table contains data on the location of the holes; the survey table contains data on the orientation at which the holes were drilled; the assay table contains the elemental analysis; and the geology table contains the rock types. A geological database was created, validated, and then composited at 2m from the four tables. The Datamine Studio RM software was used for data analysis, 3D modelling and resource estimation.

Methods

The methodology used in this study generally involves:

- Database creation and validation
- Statistical analysis
- Geological (or 3D) modelling
- Block modelling
- Variogram analysis
- Resource estimation
- Comparison of all results
- Validation

Interpolation or estimation Methods

Ordinary kriging

Geostatistics works best with spatially correlated samples to classify the deposit's natural characteristics and mineralisation trend. Geostatistical ordinary kriging interpolation employs the semi-variogram to generate the best linear unbiased estimate (BLUE) at each location (Mallick et al., 2019). To build a semi-variogram, we compare one sample value to all others at constantly increasing intervals or lags. The semi-variogram is denoted by Equ 1:

$$\gamma(h) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n [Z(X_i) - Z(X_i + h)] \quad (1)$$

Where $Z(X_i)$ is the grade at a point (X_i) in space, $Z(X_i+h)$ is the grade at another location (lag distance), and N is the pairing number.

Equ 2 denotes the block estimate.

$$Z^* = \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i Z \quad (2)$$

Where Z^* is the estimated value, λ is the sample weight coefficient, and Z represents the individual values at sample points. The weights ($\sum \lambda = 1$) must equal 1 to fulfil the unbiased situation.

Inverse Distance weighting

The inverse distance weighting (IDW) method can evaluate low to high-grade variability deposits. The method applies a weighting factor based on an inverse distance function of each sample with a set of known sample values about the central point of an unknown ore block. A general assumption is that a sample value would decrease as one moves away from a point and increase as one moves toward that point (First Law of Geography). The method is a function of distance but uses the inverse of the distance to interpolate unknown points, hence the name, inverse distance weighting method. The formula for this method is given in Equ. 3.

$$Z^* = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{Z_i}{d_i^n}}{\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{d_i^n}} \quad (3)$$

Nearest neighbour Polygon

The nearest neighbour polygon (NNP) method is one of the most straightforward interpolation techniques for calculating unsampled values. It is the most common computerised polygonal method. This method predicts the attributes of unsampled points by assigning values based on nearby polygons. Only one point or the nearest sampled point value is assigned to the point that is being estimated. The NNP method is mainly used when other robust interpolation methods are not applicable in predicting or estimating the outcome of data. It can also be used as a follow-up method to show that the robust interpolation method of estimations is within an accepted range, thus proving their precision and accuracy.

Cross-Validation

Cross-validation of the ordinary kriging interpolation method is by the use of the calculated slope of regression values. The slope of regression compares the estimated grade values with the actual grade value, and the goal is to have a mean slope or value of 1 or nearly 1. Conditional bias occurs if the mean slope value is less than 0.5 (underestimation) or greater than 1.5 (overestimation).

The three methods used in this study are validated by the global mean grade difference values, coefficient of variation value, and calculated standard error value.

RESULTS AND INTERPRETATION

Database and Statistical Analysis

A geological database is a combination of reliable tables containing drill-hole records. The database was created and validated from four tables (collar, survey, assay and geology) having information on the thirty-nine (39) reverse circulation drill holes. The collar table contains location data, the survey table contains data on the orientation at which the holes were drilled, the assay table contains the elemental analysis of %Fe, and the geology table contains the rock types. The thirty-nine (39) reverse circulation drill holes with a grid spacing of 200m x 60m were used in this study for mineral resource modelling and estimation (Figure 2). Applying the 30% Fe grade cut-off, raw assay values were composited at a 2m vertical interval downhole. Statistical analysis was performed on the raw assay data to observe and summarise the main characteristics. The histogram (Figure 3) and summary statistics (Table 1) revealed that the data is relatively normal, proving that data transformation is neglected. A kurtosis value of -0.466 in the summary statistics, which is close to zero, a skewness value of 0.486 and a low CV value of 0.624 all prove normal distribution of the data.

Figure 2: Location map of RC drill holes

Figure 3: Histogram of Iron (Fe) grades

Table 1: Summary statistics of raw data

Parameter	Value
Total Samples	1525
Minimum (%)	0.940
Maximum (%)	60.320
Mean (%)	20.460
Median (%)	19.210
Coefficient of Variation	0.624
Standard deviation	12.767
Skewness	0.486
Kurtosis	-0.466

3D Geological Model and Block Model

A 3D geological model is the visualisation of the extent and shape of the orebody below the surface. To differentiate ore/waste, a 30% iron grade cut-off was applied. The ore was modelled keenly after the grade cut-off (grade shell). A block size of 50m x 20m x 5m (Figure 4), fitting the rule of thumb practice of block size being ¼ to ½ the drill hole spacing of the deposit, was created from the geological model for mineral resource estimation. Table 2 shows the geographical extent and cell size of the block model. To validate the geological 3D model and the block model, a comparison is made between the volume of the geological model and the volume of the block model. The result in Table 3, with a percent difference of 0.29% which is lower than 2%, the expected maximum limit, shows high validity of our geological and block models.

Figure 4: A plan view of the block model

Table 2: Properties of block model showing geographical extent and cell size

	Cell size(m)	Model size		Cell count (Number)
		Min (m)	Max (m)	
X	50	252506.5	254156.50	33
Y	20	760908.10	761888.10	49
Z	5	-135.42	179.58	63
				101,871

Table 3: Validation of Geological Model and Block Model

Geological Model volume (m3)	Block Model volume (m3)	Volume difference (m3)	(%) Diff
6,248,455.49	6,230,099.17	18,356.31	0.29

Variography

A semi-variogram is needed for ordinary kriging estimation to show the spatial relationship or variability among data. It shows whether the deposit is isotropic or anisotropic. Experimental semi-variograms have been computed for Fe and fitted against a spherical theoretical model. The semi-variogram analysis revealed that the Gofolo Hill deposit is anisotropic because the range value differs in different directions. Parameters of the semi-variogram fitted using a spherical model are shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Parameters of a single structure spherical model

Type	Nugget	Sill	RANGE (m)		
			(X)	(Y)	(Z)
Spherical Model	44.2	119.0	80.8	274.7	61.7

Estimation

Resource

All three methods, ordinary kriging, inverse distance weighting and nearest neighbour polygon, were applied to estimate the resource of Gofolo Hill. The ordinary kriging method uses parameters from the semi-variogram to consider the spatial relationship and trend among data when estimating. A global cut-off grade of 30% Fe and a global density value of 3.0 kg/m³ were used to interpolate the grade blocks. The ordinary kriging method estimated the deposit to have 17.169 megatonnes of ore at a mean Fe grade of 35.90%. The inverse distance weighting method estimated the deposit to have 16.975 megatonnes at 35.53% Fe. The nearest neighbour polygon method overestimated the grade by producing 38.53% and underestimated the tonnage by producing 14.757 megatonnes. Table 5 shows the three method's grade, volume and tonnage results.

Statistics

Statistical analysis of basic parameters from the block estimation of each method is presented in Table 6. A relatively low coefficient of variation (CV) value (lower than 0.5) reported for all estimation methods shows good comparison similarity.

Correlation coefficient

The individual estimates of the three estimation methods were correlated using a scatter plot and correlation coefficient value (Figure 5). This shows how one method of estimation is related to the other. The correlation coefficient of the ordinary kriging vs. inverse distance weighting method is 0.876. The ordinary kriging compared to the nearest neighbour polygon method is 0.687. The inverse distance weighting and the nearest neighbour polygon correlation result is 0.720.

Cross-Validation

Validation of the Ordinary Kriging method block estimates was carried out by the use of the slope of regression value of each interpolated block. The slope of regression compares the actual grade with the estimated grade (Z/Z^*). The goal is to have a mean slope of regression value equal to 1 or close to 1. Figure 6 shows a histogram of the calculated slope of regression values with about 85% of the kriged estimates showing good correlation (values between 0.5 to 1) and having a mean slope of regression value of 0.792.

Valid estimated results are shown for all three methods by the values obtained from the coefficient of variation, standard error, and the global mean grade difference vs. model. Table 7 shows a standard error value that is close to 0 and a global mean grade difference vs. model value that is less than 5% meaning high accuracy.

Table 5: Grade, volume and tonnage result

METHOD	VOLUME (m ³)	TONNAGE (tonnes)	GRADE (%)
OK	5,723,145	17,169,435	35.90
IDW	5,658,375	16,975,126	35.53
NNP	4,919,024	14,757,072	38.53

Table 6: Summary statistics of all methods compared

PARAMETER	OK	IDW	NNP
Minimum	16.91	16.99	8.34
Maximum	51.71	54.91	60.32
Mean	35.00	34.54	35.17
Median	34.48	34.04	34.93
Coefficient of Variation	0.123	0.126	0.241
Standard deviation	4.32	4.36	8.46

Figure 5: Scatterplot showing the correlation of the three estimation methods

Figure 6: Histogram for the calculated slope of regression values

Table 7: Cross-validation by standard error and global mean grade difference vs. model

VALIDATION METHOD	OK	IDW	NNP
Standard Error	0.105	0.106	0.206
% Global Mean grade difference vs. Model	2.21%	0.96%	2.76%

Discussion

The Gofolo Hill iron ore deposit in Grand Cape Mount County, Western Liberia, West Africa, was estimated using three regular methods used in mineral resource estimation practices. The ordinary kriging method, referred to as the best, linear unbiased method, is often seen as the best performing method of the three since it considers trend and spatial relationship and can be evaluated to reveal the accuracy of estimation. Even without an optimal search parameter, the study shows that the ordinary kriging method outperforms the inverse distance weighting method and the nearest neighbour polygon method by producing the lowest coefficient of variation, standard deviation (and variance) and estimation error. Comparing the three methods, the inverse distance weighting method shows more comparable figures to the ordinary kriging than the nearest neighbour polygon method when comparing the grade-volume—tonnage results. Out of the six statistical parameters compared, the inverse distance weighting showed more comparable statistics to the ordinary kriging in five parameters – minimum, maximum, median, coefficient of variation and standard deviation; the nearest neighbour polygon method only showed a better comparison with the ordinary kriging method in a single parameter: the mean value. The correlation coefficient comparison also shows a higher value of 0.876 when comparing the ordinary kriging method to the inverse distance weighting method and a lower 0.687 value when comparing the ordinary kriging method with the nearest neighbour polygon method. The accuracy of all three interpolation methods is proven by the mean slope of regression value for kriging estimates, the standard error value close to zero and the percent mean grade difference vs. model that is below 5%.

CONCLUSION

The study reveals that the Gofolo Hill Iron ore deposit contains 17,169,435 tonnes of iron ore at a mean grade of 35.90 % Fe when calculated using the more accurate ordinary kriging method. The calculation was based on a global mean grade of 30% Fe and a global density of 3.00 kg/m³. The accuracy of the ordinary kriging method is proven by the lowest coefficient of variation, standard deviation (and variance) and estimation error. Comparing the grade-volume-tonnage results of the Ordinary Kriging method to the inverse distance weighting method and the nearest neighbour polygon method shows that the inverse distance weighting method produced more comparable results to the Ordinary Kriging method. The nearest neighbour polygon method overestimated the mean grade and underestimated the tonnage of the deposit. Statistical analysis and correlation coefficient value of individual estimates also show that the inverse distance weighting is more comparable to the ordinary kriging method. All methods were validated by the mean slope of regression value for kriging estimates, the standard error value close to zero and the percent mean grade difference vs. model below 5%.

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